

Characterization of heritage objects with NIR hyperspectral imaging

Jakub Sandak^{1,2*}, Anna Sandak^{1,3}, Lea Legan⁴, Klara Retko⁴, Maša Kavčič⁴, Janez Kosel⁴, Faksawat Poohphajai^{1,5}, Rene Herrera Diaz^{1,6}, Veerapandian Ponnuchamy¹, Nežka Sajinčič¹, Črtomir Tavzes^{1,4}, Polona Ropret⁴

¹ InnoRenew CoE, Livade 6, 6310 Izola, Slovenia, jakub.sandak@innorenew.eu, anna.sandak@innorenew.eu, faksawat.poohphajai@innorenew.eu, rene.herdiacz@innorenew.eu, veerapandian.ponnuchamy@innorenew.eu, nezka.sajincic@innorenew.eu, crtomir.tavzes@innorenew.eu

² University of Primorska, Andrej Marušič Institute, jakub.sandak@upr.si

³ University of Primorska, Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies, Glagoljaška 8, 6000 Koper, Slovenia, anna.sandak@famnit.upr.si

⁴ Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia, Poljanska 40, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, lea.legan@zvks.si, klara.retko@zvks.si, masa.kavcic@zvks.si, janez.kosel@zvks.si, crtomir.tavzes@zvks.si, polona.ropret@zvks.si

⁵ Aalto University, School of Chemical Engineering, Department of Bioproducts and Biosystems, P.O. Box 16300, 00076, Aalto, Finland

⁶ Chemical and Environmental Engineering Department, University of the Basque Country, San Sebastian, Spain

*Corresponding author

Numerous analytical methods might be implemented to study art objects' authenticity, composition, and conservation state. However, most of these are time consuming, expensive, or destructive. The implementation of alternative techniques having high reliability and nondestructive character is, therefore, within great interest of restorers and researchers. This work demonstrates the implementation of hyperspectral imaging (HI) for cultural heritage object evaluation. Five hyperspectral cameras produced by SPECIM (Oulu, Finland) that operate in different spectral ranges were used for scanning a beehive panel painting that was obtained from the collection of the Slovene Ethnographic Museum. All cameras were operating in push broom mode, allowing line by line spectral measurement. White (spectralon) and black (detector noise) reference backgrounds were measured before each scanning of the panel. Halogen lamps were used as a light source for VNIR, NIR, and SWIR cameras, while heat radiation was used as a source for the MWIR and LWIR systems. Evince software by Prediktera (Umea, Sweden) was used for analysing and exploring the hyperspectral images. Standard normal variate (SNV) and mean centring were applied as preprocessing prior to PCA modelling.

Precise and fast methods, such as HI, provide information related not only to certain pigments and binders used but also allow for their mapping on the entire object. The obtained score plots, in the form of spatially resolved pixels, also contain information regarding similarity, groupings, and trend patterns that characterize the object. Analysis of loadings allows identification of spectra where specific wavelengths regions contributed to high variance in certain PCA models. In our study, HI scanning was also compared with other spectroscopic methods, such as Raman and FT-IR spectroscopy, which are commonly used for the identification of pigments and binders of the investigated objects (Retko et al., 2019). Therefore, the merging of HI with other reference methods results in the generation of a rich

database that allows for a precise identification of original artist materials as well as various additives that were possibly applied later (e.g., during conservation campaigns).

Keywords: hyperspectral imaging, cultural heritage, painted beehive panels

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